

BC-SIM-TR-040

EGSE ICO#5 Report

Romolo Politi¹, Emanuele Simioni², Michele Zusi¹
Fabrizio Capaccioni¹, Alain Doressoundiram³, Yves Langevin⁴,
Pasquale Palumbo⁵, Mathieu Vincendon⁴, Gabriele Cremonese²

¹INAF- Istituto Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali, Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy

²INAF-Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Vicolo Osservatorio 5,35122, Padua, Italy

³Observatoire de Paris - PSL, Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique (LESIA), 92195 Meudon Cedex, France

⁴Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale, CNRS / Université Paris Sud, 91405, Orsay, France

⁵Università Parthenope, Centro Direzionale Isola 4, 80133, Naples, Italy

Index

INDEX	2
1 INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 SCOPE	5
1.2 REFERENCE DOCUMENT	5
1.3 ATTACHED DOCUMENT	5
1.4 ACRONYMS	5
1.5 DOCUMENT FORMAT AND REPOSITORY	6
1.6 TEST PLAN	6
1.7 REPORT SCHEMA	6
1.7.1 <i>Telecommands</i>	7
1.7.2 <i>Data Produced</i>	7
1.7.3 <i>Event Checks</i>	7
1.7.4 <i>PE Events</i>	8
1.7.5 <i>Lost Packets</i>	8
1.7.6 <i>Telecommand Check</i>	8
1.7.7 <i>Test Results</i>	8
2 PREPROCESSING	9
3 ICO#5 RESULTS ANALYSIS	10
3.1 GENERAL CONSIDERATION	10
3.2 HRIC FUNCTIONAL TEST	10
3.2.1 <i>Test Scope</i>	10
3.2.2 <i>Test Execution</i>	10
3.2.3 <i>Science</i>	11
3.2.4 <i>Data Produced</i>	11
3.2.5 <i>ME Events</i>	11
3.2.6 <i>PE Events</i>	11
3.2.7 <i>Lost Packets</i>	11
3.2.8 <i>TC Check</i>	12
3.2.9 <i>Discussion</i>	12
3.3 HRIC PERFORMANCE TEST	13
3.3.1 <i>Test Scope</i>	13
3.3.2 <i>Test Execution</i>	13
3.3.3 <i>Science</i>	13
3.3.4 <i>Data Produced</i>	13
3.3.5 <i>ME Events</i>	14
3.3.6 <i>PE Events</i>	14
3.3.7 <i>Lost Packets</i>	14
3.3.8 <i>TC Check</i>	14
3.3.9 <i>Discussion</i>	14
3.4 HRIC LOW FREQUENCIES BEHAVIOR	15
3.4.1 <i>Test Scope</i>	15
3.4.2 <i>Test Execution</i>	15
3.4.3 <i>Science</i>	15
3.4.4 <i>Data Produced</i>	15
3.4.5 <i>ME Events</i>	15
3.4.6 <i>PE Events</i>	16
3.4.7 <i>Lost Packets</i>	16
3.4.8 <i>TC Check</i>	16

Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
Date	17/05/2024		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page	3/30		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.4.9	<i>Discussion</i>	16
3.5	STC FUNCTIONAL TEST	17
3.5.1	<i>Test Scope</i>	17
3.5.2	<i>Test Execution</i>	17
3.5.3	<i>Science</i>	17
3.5.4	<i>Data Produced</i>	17
3.5.5	<i>ME Events</i>	18
3.5.6	<i>PE Events</i>	18
3.5.7	<i>Lost Packets</i>	18
3.5.8	<i>TC Check</i>	18
3.5.9	<i>Discussion</i>	18
3.6	STC PERFORMANCE TEST	19
3.6.1	<i>Test Scope</i>	19
3.6.2	<i>Test Execution</i>	19
3.6.3	<i>Science</i>	19
3.6.4	<i>Data Produced</i>	20
3.6.5	<i>ME Events</i>	20
3.6.6	<i>PE Events</i>	20
3.6.7	<i>Lost Packets</i>	20
3.6.8	<i>TC Check</i>	20
3.6.9	<i>Discussion</i>	21
3.7	STC LFB TEST	22
3.7.1	<i>Test Scope</i>	22
3.7.2	<i>Test Execution</i>	22
3.7.3	<i>Science</i>	22
3.7.4	<i>Data Produced</i>	22
3.7.5	<i>ME Events</i>	22
3.7.6	<i>PE Events</i>	22
3.7.7	<i>Lost Packets</i>	23
3.7.8	<i>TC Check</i>	23
3.7.9	<i>Discussion</i>	23
3.8	VIHI PERFORMANCE TEST	24
3.8.1	<i>Test Scope</i>	24
3.8.2	<i>Test Execution</i>	24
3.8.3	<i>Science</i>	24
3.8.4	<i>Data Produced</i>	24
3.8.5	<i>ME Events</i>	25
3.8.6	<i>PE Events</i>	25
3.8.7	<i>Lost Packets</i>	25
3.8.8	<i>TC Check</i>	25
3.8.9	<i>Discussion</i>	25
3.9	INTERFERENCE TEST	26
3.9.1	<i>Test Scope</i>	26
3.9.2	<i>Test Execution</i>	26
3.9.3	<i>Science</i>	26
3.9.4	<i>Data Produced</i>	27
3.9.5	<i>ME Error</i>	28
3.9.6	<i>PE Error</i>	28
3.9.7	<i>Lost Packets</i>	28
3.9.8	<i>TC Check</i>	28
3.9.9	<i>Discussion</i>	28
4	SUMMARY	1

Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
Date	17/05/2024		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page	4/30		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

Approval

Edited by:	
	Romolo Politi
	Emanuele Simioni
	Michele Zusi
Revised by:	
	Fabrizio Capaccioni
	Alain Doressoundiram
	Yves Langevin
	Pasquale Palumbo
	Mathieu Vincendon
Approved by:	
	Gabriele Cremonese

Document Change Record

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	5/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

In this document we will describe all the tests performed during the fifth Instrument Checkout (ICO#05) for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS). The checkout session was performed June 14th 2021. For each test it will be presented the pipeline report and, where necessary, a discussion on the detected anomalies.

1.2 Reference Document

- [RD1] BC-SIM-PL-XXX-Checkout_05_Test_Summary_Issue_1 (DOI: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11207999>)
- [RD2] BC-SIM-TN-003 - Reports and Notes Layout and Flow, Version 2 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179>)
- [RD3] BC-SIM-TR-XXX Technical Report - Software User Manual, in preparation;
- [RD4] BC-SIM-GAF-IC-002_rev12 - SIMBIO-SYS Software Interface Control Document
- [RD5] BepiColombo FOP data package 3.1
- [RD6] BC-ASD-SP-00176_1_4 SIMBIO URD
- [RD7] BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002_10_001 - SIMBIO-SYS User Manual
- [RD8] BC-SIM-TN-006_-_simClean_-_Telemetry_Filter_Tool (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/103>);

1.3 Attached Document

- [AT.1] Command_Stack_ICO05.xlsx
- [AT.2] Event_ICO05.log

1.4 Acronyms

APID	Application Process IDentifier
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
LBF	Low Frequency Behavior
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
dNECP	delta Near Earth Commissioning Phase
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
STC	STereo imaging Channel

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	6/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

TBW	To Be Written
TC	Telecommand
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1.5 Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD2] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.6 Test Plan

The ICO#5 test was planned to be executed on two days based on the tests described in [RD1].

ID	Test Description	Start	Stop
1	HRIC Functional Test	2021-06-14T14:59:00.00Z	2021-06-14T15:28:30.00Z
2	HRIC Performance Test	2021-06-14T15:30:00.00Z	2021-06-14T15:39:59.00Z
3	HRIC LFB Test	2021-06-14T15:40:00.00Z	2021-06-14T16:09:59.00Z
4	STC Functional Test	2021-06-14T16:10:00.00Z	2021-06-14T16:41:56.00Z
5	STC Performance Test	2021-06-14T16:45:00.00Z	2021-06-14T17:05:03.00Z
6	STC LFB Test	2021-06-14T17:05:05.00Z	2021-06-14T17:29:30.00Z
7	VIHI Performance Test	2021-06-14T17:30:00.00Z	2021-06-14T17:49:00.00Z
8	Interference Test	2021-06-14T18:00:00.00Z	2021-06-14T20:51:00.00Z

Table 1: Test Schedule.

1.7 Report Schema

For each test, the report will be formed by four sections created by an automatic procedure:

- a summary of all the data produced in that test;
- a report with the events and telecommand acknowledgments;
- a report of the PE events;
- a check on the lost packets.

The report includes even two sections with a comparison between the commanded TCs and the data results. Eventual problems or discrepancies will be discussed.

The complete Sections list defined for each test is shown in Table 2 and described in the subsections below.

Section #	Section Name
1	Telecommands
2	Data Procedure

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	7/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3	Events Check
4	PE Event
5	Lost packets
6	Telecommand Check
7	Discussion

Table 2: Section structure defined for each Test.

1.7.1 Telecommands

In this Section, the telecommands used for the test will be reported. For each telecommand an analysis and an evaluation of the produced data will be performed.

1.7.2 Data Produced

In this Section, a table with the data produced will be reported. The output files consist into two different types of CSVs (one for the diagnostic housekeeping and one with all the housekeeping parameters related to a single image) and a file containing the image in binary format. All data are compliant to the PDS4 format, which means that they include an XML file with all the parameters of each acquisition, both considering as source the instrument or the spacecraft. A complete description of the file structure and the folder tree is reported in [RD3]. For each image it is present an additional file in PNG format as a quick preview.

In the summary schema it will be reported the number and the total size of the following file types:

- Diagnostic HKs
- Acquisition HKs;
- Images

1.7.3 Event Checks

In the event checks section it will be reported:

- all the negative telecommand acknowledgments,
- the rejected telecommands, TM(1,2),
- the failed telecommands, TM(1,8).

For each negative event (rejected, failed or ignored telecommand), all the information about the telecommand, mnemonic name, description, time of execution, and all associated parameters are reported. For each event it is reported a list for the low severity TM(5,2), medium severity TM(5,3) and high severity TM(5,4) errors with a description of the event.

The complete list of event and telecommand acknowledgments is reported into the Event file stored in each test folder. All the information relative to an event or a telecommand acknowledgments are from [RD4].

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	8/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

1.7.4 PE Events

From an automatic analysis of the diagnostic HK, a list of the negative event alerts, sent by the PE, is created. Each alert is reported with the associated decimal ID and with its complete description. All the information relative to a PE events refers to [RD4].

1.7.5 Lost Packets

The automatic check on the lost packets is performed using the Packet Sequence Control (PSC) number (see [RD4]). The PSC is a serial number associated with the TM packets and follows a different enumeration for different APID. A list of the used APID is reported in the following table:

APID	Description
801	TC Verification
804	HK Reports
807	Event Reports
828	HRIC Data High Priority
844	STC Data High Priority
860	VIHI Data High Priority
870	HRIC Data Low Priority
892	STC Data Low Priority
908	VIHI Data Low Priority

Table 3: List of the APIDs associated to each dataflow.

The PSC number is stored in 14 bits. This means that the maximum value is 16383. After that, the counter restart from 0.

NB: A manual check-in is required in order to evaluate if some packets are lost at the beginning and the end of the acquisition. The automatic check detects only holes in the PSC sequence.

1.7.6 Telecommand Check

In this Section it is checked that the ME and the PE have executed all received telecommand.

1.7.7 Test Results

In this Section we will discuss the results, the discrepancies, and the errors if they are present.

Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
Date	17/05/2024		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page	9/30		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

2 Preprocessing

The TM file downloaded from the EDDS server has been preprocessed using the simClean tools [RD8] to remove the duplicate HK and the duplicated science packets due to the reception of the same one by different antennas.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	10/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3 ICO#5 Results Analysis

3.1 General consideration

With reference to Table 4, we report the following quality table:

ID	Test Name	Test result
01	HRIC Functional Test	
02	HRIC Performance Test	
03	HRIC LFB	
04	STC Functional Test	
05	STC Performance Test	
06	STC LFB	
07	VIHI Performance Test	
08	Interference Test	

Table 4: Quality table.

for which we use the following color keys in the last column:

- Red:** test failed;
- Yellow:** test partially passed;
- Green:** Test passed.

3.2 HRIC Functional Test

3.2.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is:

- to check the status and the functionality of the following electric components of the channel:
 - PE;
 - Detector;
 - TEC;
- to modify some configuration parameters;
- to perform some science acquisitions.

3.2.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T14:59:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T15:28:30.00Z

In Table 5 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF

Table 5: Instrument status before the HRIC Functional Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	11/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.2.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following three science sessions have been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1737	6 minutes	Continuous	2.0	181	181
1	---	6 minutes	---	---	181	181

Table 6: Description of the TC used during HRIC Functional Test.

Table 6 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the Functional Test.

3.2.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	578.5 kB

Bundle Raw HRIC			
File	CSV		
		#	181
		Size	164.3 kB
	DAT		
		#	181
		Size	95.1 MB

Table 7: Data produced during the HRIC Functional Test.

3.2.5 ME Events

None

3.2.6 PE Events

None

3.2.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	46	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	1338	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	7	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC low Priority	905	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 8: Packets and lost packet report for the HRIC Functional Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	12/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.2.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	23
Executed	23
Refuted	0
Failed	0

Table 9: TC report for the HRIC Functional Test.

3.2.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 10 with information from section 3.2.3 and 3.2.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	181	181
Science Sessions	1	1

Table 10: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the HRIC Functional Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	13/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.3 HRIC Performance Test

3.3.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is to perform several acquisitions in dark condition and variable integration times to monitor the DC evolution during the cruise phase.

3.3.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T15:30:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T15:39:59.00Z

In Table 11 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
ON	ON	OFF	OFF

Table 11: Instrument status before the HRIC Performance Test.

3.3.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science session has been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1740	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
2	1741	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
3	1742	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
4	1743	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
5	1744	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
6	1745	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
7	1746	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
8	1747	18 seconds	Limited	2.0	9	9
9	1748	36 seconds	Limited	4.0	9	9
9	---	1 minute and 57 seconds	---	---	81	81

Table 12: Description of the TC used during HRIC Performance Test.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1740	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
2	1741	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
3	1742	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
4	1743	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
5	1744	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
6	1745	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
7	1746	9 seconds	Limited	1.0	9	9
8	1747	18 seconds	Limited	2.0	9	9
9	1748	36 seconds	Limited	4.0	9	9
9	---	1 minute and 57 seconds	---	---	81	81

Table 12 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the Performance Test.

3.3.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	14/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

	Size	15.0 kB
--	------	---------

Bundle Raw HRIC		
File	CSV	
	#	81
	Size	73.5 kB
DAT	#	81
	Size	212.4 MB

Table 13: Data produced during the HRIC Performance Test.

3.3.5 ME Events

None.

3.3.6 PE Events

None.

3.3.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	18	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	40	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	18	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC low Priority	45441	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 14: Packets and lost packet report for the HRIC Performance Test.

3.3.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	9
Executed	9
Refuted	0
Failed	0

Table 15: TC report for the HRIC Performance Test.

3.3.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 16 with information from section 3.3.3 and 3.3.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	81	81
Science Sessions	9	9

Table 16: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the HRIC Performance Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	15/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.4 HRIC Low Frequencies Behavior

3.4.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if and how HRIC detector reset fluctuations change with respect to the Repetition Time parameter contained in their Science TC.

3.4.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T15:40:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T16:09:59.00Z

In Table 17 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
ON	ON	OFF	OFF

Table 17: Instrument status before the HRIC LFB Test.

3.4.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science sessions have been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1750	7 minutes	Continuous	0.8	525	525
2	1751	6 minutes and 58 seconds	Continuous	4.0	105	104
3	1752	6 minutes and 56 seconds	Continuous	8.0	52	52
3	---	20 minutes and 56 seconds	---	---	682	681

Table 18: Description of the TC used during HRIC LFB Test.

Table 18 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the LFB Test.

3.4.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	583.0 kB

Bundle Raw HRIC			
File	CSV		
		#	683
		Size	620.2 kB
	DAT		
		#	683
		Size	90.1 MB

Table 19: Data produced during the HRIC LFB Test.

3.4.5 ME Events

None.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	16/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.4.6 PE Events

None.

3.4.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	10	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	1349	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	3	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC low Priority	1366	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC low Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI low Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 20: Packets and lost packet report for the HRIC LFB Test.

3.4.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	5
Executed	5
Refuted	0
Failed	0

Table 21: TC report for the HRIC LFB Test.

3.4.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 16 with information from section 3.4.3 and 3.4.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	81	81
Science Sessions	9	9

Table 22: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the HRIC LFB Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	17/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.5 STC Functional Test

3.5.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is:

- to check the status and the functionality of the following electric components of the channel:
 - PE,
 - Detector and
 - TEC;
- to modify some configuration parameters.
- to perform some science acquisitions.

3.5.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T16:10:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T16:41:56.00Z.

In Table 23 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF

Table 23: Instrument status before the STC Functional Test.

3.5.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science sessions have been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1774	20 seconds	Continuous	2.0	10	30
2	1775	2 minutes and 10 seconds	Continuous	12.3	11	33
3	1776	4.70 seconds	Continuous	0.4	12	60
4	1777	23.90 seconds	Continuous	2.05	12	60
5	1780	8 minutes and 59.30 seconds	Continuous	2.0	270	270
5	---	12 minutes and 4 seconds	---	---	315	453

Table 24: Description of the TC used during STC Performance Test.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1774	20 seconds	Continuous	2.0	10	30
2	1775	2 minutes and 10 seconds	Continuous	12.3	11	33
3	1776	4.70 seconds	Continuous	0.4	12	60
4	1777	23.90 seconds	Continuous	2.05	12	60
5	1780	8 minutes and 59.30 seconds	Continuous	2.0	270	270
5	---	12 minutes and 4 seconds	---	---	315	453

Table 24 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the Performance Test.

3.5.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	582.5 kB

Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
Date	17/05/2024		
Issue	1	Revision	0
Page	18/30		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

Bundle Raw STC			
File	CSV		
		#	453
		Size	416.8 kB
DAT			
		#	453
		Size	45.5 MB

Table 25: Data produced during the STC Functional Test.

3.5.5 ME Events

None.

3.5.6 PE Events

None.

3.5.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	58	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	1332	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	5	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC low Priority	1869	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 26: Packets and lost packet report for the STC Functional Test.

3.5.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	29
Executed	29
Rejected	0
Failed	0

Table 27: TC report for the STC Functional Test.

3.5.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 28 with information from section 3.5.3 and 3.5.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	453	453
Science Sessions	5	5

Table 28: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the STC Functional Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	19/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.6 STC Performance Test

3.6.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is to acquire the Dark Current in order to study its evolution during the cruise phase and to test the Mitigate strategy to be used in CM to mitigate the DC reset for a long waiting time.

3.6.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T16:45:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T17:05:03.00Z.

In Table 29 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
ON	OFF	ON	OFF

Table 29: Instrument status before the STC Performance Test.

3.6.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science session has been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1783	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
2	1784	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
3	1785	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
4	1786	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
5	1787	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
6	1788	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
7	1789	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	30
8	1790	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
9	1791	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
10	1792	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
11	1793	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
12	1794	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
13	1795	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
14	1796	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	30
15	1797	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
16	1798	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
17	1799	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
18	1800	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
19	1801	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
20	1802	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
21	1803	4 seconds	Limited	0.45	10	20
22	1804	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
23	1805	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
24	1806	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
25	1807	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
26	1808	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
27	1809	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
28	1810	1 minute and 10 seconds	Limited	7.0	10	20
28	---	17 minutes and 23 seconds	---	---	280	700

Table 30: Description of the TC used during STC Functional Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	20/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

Table 30 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the Performance Test.

3.6.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	30.8 kB

Bundle Raw STC			
File	CSV		
		#	700
		Size	644.0 kB
	DAT		
		#	700
		Size	90.1 MB

Table 31: Data produced during the STC Performance Test.

3.6.5 ME Events

None.

3.6.6 PE Events

None.

3.6.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	58	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	83	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	56	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC low Priority	13189	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 32: Packets and lost packet report for the STC Performance Test.

3.6.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	29
Executed	29
Refiuted	0
Failed	0

Table 33: TC report for the STC Performance Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	21/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.6.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 34 with information from section 3.6.3 and 3.6.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	700	700
Science Sessions	28	28

Table 34: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the STC Performance Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	22/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.7 STC LFB Test

3.7.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if and how the STC detector reset fluctuations change with respect to the Repetition Time parameter contained in their Science TC.

3.7.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T17:05:05.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T17:29:30.00Z

In Table 35 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
ON	OFF	ON	OFF

Table 35: Instrument status before the STC Performance Test.

3.7.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science session has been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1812	7 minutes	Continuous	0.8	525	525
2	1813	6 minutes and 58 seconds	Continuous	7.0	60	60
3	1814	7 minutes and 1 second	Continuous	12.3	35	35
3	---	20 minutes and 58 seconds	---	---	620	620

Table 36: Description of the TC used during STC LFB Test.

3.7.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	586.0 kB

Bundle Raw STC			
File	CSV		
		#	620
		Size	570.4 kB
	DAT		
		#	620
		Size	10.7 MB

Table 37: Data produced during the STC LFB Test.

3.7.5 ME Events

None.

3.7.6 PE Events

None.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	23/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.7.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	8	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	1334	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	3	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC low Priority	620	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 38: Packets and lost packet report for the STC LFB Test.

3.7.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	4
Executed	4
Rejected	0
Failed	0

Table 39: TC report for the STC LFB Test.

3.7.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 40 with information from section 3.7.3 and 3.7.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	620	620
Science Sessions	3	3

Table 40: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the STC LFB Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	24/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.8 VIHI Performance Test

3.8.1 Test Scope

The test will be devoted to the accurate description and understanding of the Dark Current management.

3.8.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T17:30:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T17:49:00.00Z

In Table 41 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF

Table 41: Instrument status before the VIHI Performance Test.

3.8.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science session has been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1834	3 seconds	Continuous	0.13	24	24
2	1835	3.01 seconds	Continuous	0.13	24	24
3	1836	3.02 seconds	Continuous	0.16	20	20
4	1837	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	12	12
5	1840	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	12	12
6	1841	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	8	8
7	1842	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	6	6
8	1843	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	4	4
9	1844	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	6	6
10	1845	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	2	2
11	1846	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	3	3
12	1847	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	2	2
12	---	36 seconds	---	---	123	123

Table 42: Description of the TC used during VIHI Functional Test.

Table 42 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the Performance Test.

3.8.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	811.1 kB

Bundle Raw VIHI			
File	CSV		
		#	123
		Size	176.9 kB
	DAT		

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	25/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

	#	123
	Size	13.9 MB

Table 43: Data produced during the VIHI Performance Test.

3.8.5 ME Events

None.

3.8.6 PE Events

None.

3.8.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	68	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	1174	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	5	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI low Priority	3167	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 44: Packets and lost packet report for the VIHI Performance Test.

3.8.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	34
Executed	34
Rejected	0
Failed	0

Table 45: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the VIHI Performance Test.

3.8.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 46 with information from section 3.8.3 and 3.8.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	134	24
Science Sessions	9	1

Table 46: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the VIHI Performance Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	26/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.9 Interference test

3.9.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if and how the cameras (i.e., HRIC and STC) detector reset fluctuations change with respect to the Repetition Time parameter contained in their Science TC. In addition, the test will indicate if the operativity of the VIHI channel influences or not such a fluctuation.

3.9.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-06-14T18:00:00.00Z ÷ 2021-06-14T20:51:00.00Z

In Table 47 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
OFF	OFF	OFF	ON

Table 47: Instrument status before the Interference Test.

3.9.3 Science

3.9.3.1 HRIC

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1859	30 minutes and 20 seconds	Continuous	1.5	1213	1213
2	1866	46 minutes and 23 seconds	Continuous	1.005	2769	2769
2	---	1 hour, 16 minutes and 42 seconds	---	---	3982	3982

Table 48: Description of the science TC used by HRIC during the Interference Test.

3.9.3.2 STC

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1852	30 minutes and 20 seconds	Continuous	1.5	1214	1214
2	1865	46 minutes and 20 seconds	Continuous	1.0	2780	2780
2	---	1 hour, 16 minutes and 39 seconds	---	---	3994	3994

Table 49: Description of the science TC used by STC during the Interference Test.

3.9.3.3 VIHI

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1851	10 minutes	Continuous	1.0	600	600
2	1853	10 minutes	Continuous	1.0	600	600
3	1854	10 minutes and 20 seconds	Continuous	1.0	620	620
4	1858	10 minutes	Continuous	1.0	600	600
5	1860	10 minutes	Continuous	1.0	600	600
6	1861	10 minutes and 20 seconds	Continuous	1.0	620	620
6	---	1 hour and 40 seconds	---	---	3640	3640

Table 50: Description of the science TC used by VIHI during the Interference Test.

In Figure 1 is shown the TC timeline.

Figure 1: TC Timeline for the Interchannel test.

3.9.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	4
		Size	9. MB

Bundle Raw HRIC			
File	CSV	#	3984
		Size	3.6 MB
		DAT	
	#	3984	
	Size	525.8 MB	

Bundle Raw STC			
File	CSV	#	3994
		Size	3.7 MB
		DAT	
	#	3994	
	Size	69.1 MB	

Bundle Raw VIHI			
File	CSV	#	3640
		Size	5.2 MB
		DAT	
	#	3640	
	Size	64.9 MB	

Table 51: Data produced during the Interference Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	28/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.9.5 ME Error

None.

3.9.6 PE Error

None.

3.9.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	38	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	16999	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	19	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC low Priority	7968	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC low Priority	3994	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI low Priority	3640	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 52: Packets and lost packet report for the Interference Test.

3.9.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	19
Executed	19
Refuted	0
Failed	0

Table 53: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the Interference Test.

3.9.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what is expected.

The details are reported in Table 54, Table 55, and Table 56 with information from section 3.9.3 and 3.9.4.

3.9.9.1 HRIC

	Commanded	From TM
Images	3984	3984
Science Sessions	2	2

Table 54: Comparison between data commanded and produced by HRIC for the Interference Test.

3.9.9.2 STC

	Commanded	From TM
Images	3994	3994
Science Sessions	2	2

Table 55: Comparison between data commanded and produced by STC for the Interference Test.

	Document	BC-SIM-TR-040 - EGSE ICO#5 Report		
	Date	17/05/2024		
	Issue	1	Revision	0
	Page	29/30		
	DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11236096		

3.9.9.3 VIHI

	Commanded	From TM
Images	3640	3640
Science Sessions	6	6

Table 56: Comparison between data commanded and produced by VIHI for the Interference Test.

4 Summary

ID	Test description	Test Last	Science Sessions	Data from TLM [Mb]							# Images			Failure									
				HK	HRIC LP	STC LP	VIHI LP	HRIC HP	STC HP	VIHI HP	HRIC	STC	VIHI	HRIC			STC			VIHI			
														TC	ME	PE	TC	ME	PE	TC	ME	PE	
01	HRIC Functional Test	6m	1	0.16	95.1	0	0	0	0	0	181	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
02	HRIC Performance Test	1m 57s	9	0.07	212.4	0	0	0	0	0	81	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
03	HRIC LFB Test	20m 56s	3	0.62	90.1	0	0	0	0	0	683	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
04	STC Functional Test	12m 4s	5	0.41	0	45.5	0	0	0	0	0	453	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
05	STC Performance Test	17m 23s	28	0.64	0	90.1	0	0	0	0	0	700	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
06	STC LFB Test	20m 58s	3	0.57	0	10.7	0	0	0	0	0	620	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
07	VIHI Performance Test	36s	12	0.18	0	0	13.9	0	0	0	0	0	123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
08	Interference Test	2h 51m	10	12.5	525.8	69.1	64.9	0	0	0	3984	3994	3640										
08		4h 15m 54s	71	37.97	983.4	215.4	78.8	0	5505.53	0	4929	5767	3763	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 57: ICO#05 Summary of all the tests.

Data Volume [Mb]	
HRIC	983.4
STC	215.4
VIHI	78.8
	1277.6

Table 58: Data volume produced in the ICO#05